

19th BISOP

Belgrade International Symposium on Pain
May 18th 2024, Hotel Crowne plaza, Belgrade

ZBORNİK PREDAVANJA – 19. BISOP

19. beogradski internacionalni simpozijum o bolu
Beograd 18. maj 2024.
Hotel Crowne plaza, Beograd

PROCEEDINGS 19th BISOP

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THE BEST ORIGINAL WORK-THE SECOND PLACE

Postoperative pain therapy after scoliosis surgery in pediatric patients

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Introduction: Scoliosis represents the most common spinal deformity in children, which can be treated conservatively or surgically. Surgical correction of scoliosis constitutes an extensive surgical procedure that falls under painful procedures and requires adequate analgesia. Additionally, children and adolescents have lower pain tolerance, which leads to higher susceptibility to pain stimuli in comparison to adult population. Systematic analgesia is often accomplished using oral and parenteral routes, while intramuscular administration of analgesic drugs is not preferred. A multimodal approach to pain therapy has shown the possibility of better pain control with less dependence from opioids. This strategy is very important in spine surgery, because it is almost impossible to secure adequate postoperative analgesia using only one type of medication. The aim of this study was to emphasize the significance of a multimodal approach in the management of postoperative pain and to demonstrate the use of analgesics in the treatment of postoperative pain in corrective surgeries for scoliosis in children.

Methods: This study represents a clinical retrospective study conducted at the Department of Pediatric Surgery in Novi Sad, including all patients operated on from February 2020 to November 2022. From medical documentation main informations were obtain concerning: diagnosis, comorbidities, American Society of Anesthesiologist status, postoperative pain management and Visual analog scale values, length of stay in the intensive care unit and total hospitalization period.

Results: The study included 31 patients aged 8 to 18 years. There were significantly more female subjects, with an average body weight of 50.48 kg. The most present form of scoliosis .was idiopathic (70.79%). More than half of the subjects had American Society of Anesthesiologist II status and no associated comorbidities. During induction of anesthesia, an average of 103.22±43.02 micrograms of fentanyl was given. Patients

received remifentanyl on average 23.05 ± 14.1 minutes before surgery, minimum 5 and a maximum of 65 minutes before surgery. Postoperative pain management was carried out using opioid analgesics remifentanyl, morphine, and tramadol in combination with non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs and acetaminophen. Morphine was used in 27 (87.01%) patients with the average dose of 0.07 mg/kg. The number of doses of the used drugs ranged from 1 to 6, with an average of 2-3 doses per day of each individual drug. The most pronounced pain according to the Visual analog scale occurred on the postoperative day zero, with peaks at 2 to 4 hours and 8 to 12 hours, but it was of low to moderate intensity, up to 2.5. Between 48 and 72 h after surgery, another significant decrease in pain was present. The length of stay in the intensive care unit averaged 2.4 days, with a total hospitalization period averaging 9.48 days.

Conclusion: Surgical correction of scoliosis induces intense postoperative pain. A multimodal approach to postoperative pain management leads to a more successful patient recovery and improves the quality of life.

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